

IMPORTANCE OF ASCENDANT AND IT'S LORD TO BE STRENGTH

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Abstract:

It is an astrological theory that man determines his life by the name of destiny. To define this, the planetary positions and combinations in Janana Jatakas/Natal Chart help us to some extent to confirm that. With characters of the planet, they are divided into two groups like Subar and Asubar. And further, within the nine planets there are benefic planets and malefic planets. Benefic and malefic are determined depending of its origin first, Athipatyam as they acquired is next and their placements in the Janana Jataka at the last. There are many times benefic planets doesn't work with their original part and thus the horoscope never partly or fully enjoyed the beneficial of the favorable transits. Here our predictions fall as false. So, the Purpose of this research study in general, somewhat the circumstances arises the Jatakas are not able to experience those best yogas and sometimes experience negative results despite the appearance of the planets in the Janana Jataka in various excellent yogic systems. This research paper on Importance of Lagnam and Lagna Lord to be in Strength to lead whether the yogas are rains on their life or Yogas becomes ruins and Mirage (Kannal Neerana Yogangal). Here is some example Horoscopes to explain the planetary formations with examples of their causes and circumstances.

Key Words: Lagnam, Lagnathipathy, Adhipatyam, Yogam/Yogas, Bavagam/Bava, Planets, Chaya Planets and Orbits/Planetary Positions.

Introduction:

What is Yogams ? What it means ? Yogam in astrological means, conjunction of planets. Planets while on transiting in any Rasi or Zodiac sign as alone or more than one conjunct transit is known as Yogam. That means the conjunction or orbits one or more than a planet in any Zodiac sign implies Yogam. Such transits or conjunction impacts on the prediction of the natal chart and life of the particular horoscope. Also such yogam/conjunction gives benefic or malefic is depends the nature of the planet, aathipathyam of the planet, relationship between the planets and the Bava where occupied in the origin of particular horoscope. The aim of the research is to analyze that, there are many horoscopes having one or more benefic yogams on their Natal chart, because unfortunates of the Lagnam, the Jadhagar never experienced benefits throughout his/her life. However, here I given four explained horoscopes with the reality and the importance of strength of, Ascendant and the Lord of Ascendant (Lagnam and Lagna Lord).

Planets and Yogas:

As we all know that, there are seven planets Sun, Moon, Mars, Mercury, Jupiter, Venus and Saturn. In these the Sun and Moon are called as luminaries and other five are major planets. Except these seven there are two nodal points or you can say cutting points of the Moon is called Ragu and Kethu or Chaya Giragham. Now-a-days the Ragu and Kethu as known as Chaya Giragham/ imaginary planets are given much important to taken prediction over any horoscope. This is also correct in one way, because, the nodes giving more luminous/darkness to particular position where the transits happens. Any bavagam falls in to this luminous/darkness or midpoint of these ragu and kethu becomes mostly powerless and giving unwanted experience to the horoscope. Also the Ragu and Kethu where they transits they assumes that Rasi/Bava as their own house and the planets conjunct with them are become powerless. So the karagathuvam/benefic/malefic of any planet conjunct with ragu and kethu will be provided by these Chaya Planets. Before going to see the example charts, here are some definitions of formation of yogam and its names. As I already said, that, transit as a single or conjunction of more than one planet in any Rasi/Bava is called Yogam. The name of the yogam, differ and depends on the planets and its positions. Also there are hundreds of yogam which are benefic or malefic depend its position of natal chart.

Pancha Maha Purusha Yogam:

This is five yogam formed by the all five major planets Mars, Mercury, Jupiter, Venus and Saturn. In natal chart if Mars orbits at Aries, Scorpio and Capricorn the Yogam called as Rucha Yogam. If anyone having this yogam is person having quality of leadership, well developed body and vociferous. With Mercury the Bhatra yogam formed. When Mercury transits in Gemini or Virgo in Natal Chart the Yogam is formed. It gives the person in strong mind, cleverness and good personality. Jupiter's transit on Cancer, Sagittarius and Pisces in natal chart is the indication of Hamsa Yogam. The person with Hamsa yogam expect self-respect, straight forward, beauty and luxurious. Malavya Yogam means when Mercury orbits in any natal chart in places Taurus,

Libra and Pisces. Gives the person who have these is, healthy, wealthy, happy, beautiful life partner, good children, luxurious vehicles with famous and educated. In natal chart Saturn orbiting in Libra, Capricorn and Aquarius is known as Sasa Yogam. A person having sasa yogam is the person of political power, an abundant wealth, good servants, intrigues with woman, head of small groups or small village and long live.

Subha Karthari and Papakarthari Yogam:

When 2nd and 12th bava of the Ascendant occupied by benefic planets is called as Subha Karthari whereas 2nd and 12th bava occupied by malefic planets is called Papakarthati yogam. Papakarthari is one of Asuba yogam gives negative results to the Ascendant. It weakens the Ascendant.

Maha Bhagya Yogam:

This yogam is two types differing for man and woman, and day and night. In case of Male if born at day time, the Ascendant, Sun and Moon are orbits at Odd Signs then the horoscope is formed with Maha Bhagya Yogam. Whereas for the woman if the birth at night and the Ascendant, Sun and Moon orbits at Even Signs. The yogam is the indication of the person having good physique, noble, rich, honest, handsome, well educated, will enjoy all good things and comfort in life.

Pushkala Yogam:

When the Ascendant Lord conjunct with Moon and orbits at Angular (Kendra) or any friendly Rasi, and the Ascendant aspect with benefic planet then the Puskala Yogam formed. Born with Pushkala yogam means the horoscope will enjoy with wealth, ornaments, honor, famous, soft spoken and honored by the government.

Gaja Keshari Yogam:

The Moon transit in Angular/Kendra to the Jupiter is known as Gaja Keshari Yogam. Any person born in this yogam like a lion in strength and destroy his enemies. Emotional, passionate, long live, noble, intelligent and conquer by his own valor is the characteristic.

Sagatai Yogam:

This also based on transits of Moon and Jupiter. When Moon transits 6th, 8th or 12th bava to the Jupiter is called Sagatai Yogam. This yogam gives the results of, like rotating wheel. Nothing is permanent. Jathagar faces often unfortunate in his life. Luck and bad luck will play in his life. He gain and loss and regain and lost what he regain. Life goes very ordinary and with mental affect. However, if Moon orbits in Angular position to Ascendant, even if it is transits at the position of 6,8 or 12 to the Jupiter then the Sagatai doesn't works.

Lakshmi Yogam:

This yogam based on Venus. If the lord of 9th and Venus positioned in their own or if the Venus orbits Pisces as Angular/Trines to the Ascendant is formed as Lakshmi Yogam. It means the horoscope is recipient of blessings from the Goddess Lakshmi the well-known Goddess for wealth. Above are some definitions about some yogam. Now here taken for research and explaining four horoscopes which are having benefic yogam in their Natal Chart. As a formal look all charts are good in wealth and health, but in their real life they found there was no yogam has been helped them to overcome from their unfortunates. Here are the analyzed reasons why the yogam doesn't works.

Example Natal Chart 1:

Male from Kovilpatti, Tamil Nadu, Date of Birth: 20 Feb 1994, Time of birth: 0716 Hrs.

	Sa Su	Mo Ke	
// Ve(Me)	Rasi		Ve Ke
Ma	Ra	Ju	(Me)

//		La	Ju
Amsam	Mo Ma		
Sa Su	Ra		

Above horoscope, Aquarius Lagnam, 2nd and 11th lord Dhanakarakan Jupiter in self star, and orbits in 9th bava and aspects the Lagna with 5th aspect, Moon on its own star and transits in Risabam the Lagna 4th* bava from the ascendant house, 5th bava lord and 9th* bava lord together transit in Lagnam. Gives an overall view of this horoscope, Looks like an excellent beneficial horoscope. But the Natal Chart, the Lagna which falls the mid-point of Rahu Ketu indicates Jataka who is born to experience the benefits of Sanjitha Karma. Planets transiting in their grip and realizes the importance of Lagnam in Natal chart.

Jatakar's education is not beyond 8th standard even the natal chart got Bhutha Aathiya Yogam. The Jatakar who, experienced many hardships like family poverty while the Dhana Karakan Jupiter in 9th bava, lived in hidden place for a while due to debt problems.

* Refer Vedhalingapattar's Jadhaga Parijadham Lyric 193. Page 20

At the young age, because of the Sun transit on the Lagnam, the Jatakar is enjoyed the disadvantage of

Venus even though he is in a friendly house to the ascendant. A brief study of transit positions associated with Dasa Buddhis will tell us the importance of Lagnam to be in strength.

Benefic transit in Horoscope/Lagnam:

- The Lagna lord Saturn in Lagnam is special. Sasa Yogam
- The transit of Purva Punyadipati 5th lord Mercury/Budhan in Lagnam.
- It is also good that Lagna Sukasthanadipati 4th bava lord and Bhakiyadipati 9th bava lord Venus also in Lagnam. Puskala Yogam and Lakshmi yogam.
- Ascendant with triangular lords conjunct the Lagna lord in Ascendant which seems beneficial.
- Chatur and Saptama Kendradipati in conjunction with Lagnadipati.
- Exalted transits of 3rd and 10th bava lord.
- In addition to this Lagna 2nd bava lord Dana Karakan Guru is aspecting Lagnam from Lagna 9th bava.

Even though all these good transits and Yogam have been established, Jatakar's education is not good. Faces Great difficulty in the economy with poor family back ground. For this we will analyze the reasons how the Lagnam got spoiled by the planets with its Aathipathyam and relationship between them.

Unbeneficial transit of Planets in Natal Chart:

- Ascendant lord Saturn himself as vyaya bhavthipathy (12th Bava) and sits Ascendant and the sun in Lagna is point of draw back with lagnathipathy.
- Bhuthan/Purvapuniyadhipati got retrograded and he himself is the 8th bava lord and positioned in Lagnam.
- Ascendant is placed in Aquarius and the benefic lord Venus is also the padagatipati and sits in the ascendant.
- The Jupiter in the hostile house transits in 6th house to 4th bava/Sugasthanam.
- Above all, Lagnam with all the planets like Sun, Venus, Mercury and Saturn sitting in Lagnam, another tithi sunya house got the star of Rahu which is transiting in Scorpio.
- Also except Jupiter all the planets are in the grip of Rahu and Ketu and planetary and their transit is towards Ketu.

Example Natal Chart 2:

A Female chart native of Trichy, Tamil Nadu, born 11 Dec 1954, Birth time 01.50 am

		Ke Mo	
Ma	RASI	(Ju)	
		Ma Ke	
Ra	Su Me Sa Ve La		

Ve Sa			
Su		La Ra	
AMSAM			
(Ju)			
Me	Mo		

This is also a identical Horoscope. While on Venus is in 2nd bava, Moon at the 10th bava, Jupiter is placed in 11th bava and if Laganam is Virgo then the Jadhagar/woman will get great wealth. Also, this horoscope says being the 7th bava lord orbits on 11th bava then her husband will also be a famous and rich in position. And the Saturn, the lords of 4th and 5th bava orbits in exalted at Libra also a good show. The Mars, lords of 8th bava transits at 6th bava is supposed to give her the Vibareetha Dhanayogam. And the conjunction of Jupiter and Mercury indicates the horoscopes having the Bhutha Aditya yogam which is well known for education talent. Whereas, the Jadhagar survived with ordinary in education, had financially modest family life before and after marriage.

After getting married, there was a big loss in business for her husband and he moved to another place. Because of the loss in business her husband went abroad for 21/2 years and unable to get back again to the abroad job, hence, the family run with their previous savings and become economically weak. Now let us examine why the yogam in this horoscope are became useless.

Ascendant or the Lord of Ascendant once lost its strength then yogams also became useless. Here also the Lagnam lies in the mid-point of Chaya Planets and gets grip. Again the Lagna Lord Mercury gets Asthangam with Sun and orbits at the third bava the bava itself falls Bhava Katri Yogam. There it strongly we come to one conclusion that, any of Yogam in any horoscope will gives its fruits only if the Laganam and Lagna Lord should be in strengthen in position.

And the 4th and 7th bava lord the Jupiter, orbits at cancer which shows it is in exalted position, but the Jupiter get retrograded thus given the result of debilitated. So the Horoscopes health and the sukasthanam also the life partner are affected. Also the aspects of the Jupiter gives its debilitated affects to the 3rd, 5th and 7th bava. And by the rule Jupiter will give bad results to the orbiting bava/rasi. So the 11th bava of the horoscope also get affected by the Jupiter and the Jadhagar lost her most of the Karagathduva of the 11th bava. The trines are empty

and there was no planets thus it's a clear indication that this type of horoscopes not at all going to get any improvements regarding their financial and poor life style. And the Moon at the Karma sthanam conjunct with Kethu is clear indication of the horoscope born in the world to enjoy Sanchitha Karma which shown as empty.

So, here also the horoscope which shown there are three planets in exalted position, but the benefits of that planets were not enjoyed by the Jadhagar. Because of, Lagnam and the Lagnathipathy in unfavorable position, taught us importance of strength of Lagnam.

Example Natal Chart 3:

A Female Horoscope Born 21 September 1955 at Kumbakonam, Tamil Nadu, On Wednesday Birth time: 04.38 PM

	Ke	Ve Ju	Sa
La	RASI		Ju Su
		Ma	
Ra	Mo Sa	Me Su	Ve

Ra			
AMSAM			
	Mo		
La	Ma	Me	Ke

Looking on the Natal Chart, Born in Aquarius/Kumbam as Lagnam. Lagnathipathy Saturn transits in Libra/Tulam in exalted position. The 2nd and 11th bavathipathy or Dhanakaragan and Labathipathy in exalted position at Cancer, another Trine planet 5th bava Mercury transaction with Venus the 9th bavathipathy / packiyathipathy which shows the horoscope is very good and born to enjoy the wealth and health. But the scenario is totally different. Jadhagar ill literate and from poor family. She married with a gentleman who works as cook with irregular job and insufficient income. After having good signs in this horoscope the Jadhagar pulled her life with poverty and sadness. Here the through analyze, there are some important points has been found for her unfortunate is as follows:

- First and foremost the Lagnam under the grip of Chaya planets, that is falls in mid-point with Ragu and Kethu thus becomes un favor and powerless.
- The Lagnathipathy transits in exalted position but conjunct with the 8th bavathipathy.
- Lagnathipathy in exalted position aspects from its 10th view to another exalted planet Jupiter orbits in Cancer. Which will give negative effect with proverb “Uchcheanai Uchan parthal Pitchi Ettuppan” which means any exalted planet aspects another exalted planet in any zodiac the horoscope life will goes to begging position depends on its bavaga Karagam. Here the Dhanabavagam and 11th bava has been affected.
- Again the 2nd bavathipathy got exalted but orbits in the 6th bava to Lagnam, where it couldn't show and give goodness to the horoscope
- The 4th and 9th bavathipathy in debilitate position and also transaction with 8th bavathipathy.
- Another (Angular) Sapthama Kedrathipathy Sun orbits at eight bava also not in favor to the horoscope. However, she had three kids, two females and one male.
- Born Saturn's Dasa and crossed Mercury, Kethu, Venus and Sun which all are given her unfavorable life.

However, this is also example horoscope, where lagnam falls in the mid-point of Ragu and Kethu, will spoils all the yoga of any horoscope.

Example Natal Chart 4:

Male Horoscope born on 15 December 1968, born at Thiruchy, Tamil Nadu, Time of Birth 0945 PM.

Ra Sa			
Ve	RASI		La
Su Me		Mo	Ma Ke Ju

	Su Ke	Me Ve	
La Sa	Ju		
AMSAM			
	Mo	Ra	Ma

A Male Horoscope. Looking to the position of the planets.

- Cancer the Ascendant. The star of Ascendant stands Ashlesha 3rd part.
- At the third bava Jupiter, Mars and Kethu conjunct.
- And at Libra 4th bava of the horoscope, Lagnathipathy Moon Transits as Dig Balam and Pushkala

yogam.

- The Sun and Mercury transits at Sagittarius though the Mercury third bava lord transaction (Parivarthana Yogam) with the sixth bava lord Jupiter.
- Venus the fourth Angular planet transits at seventh Angular position thus gives the horoscope “Lakshmi Yogam”.
- Also the Jupiter the ninth bava lord conjunct with Mars the tenth bava lord orbits at the third bava gives him a “Dharma Karmathi Yogam”.
- And finally at 9th bava Saturn and Ragu transits and conjunct.

By these transactions of Zodiac looks to be sound in health, wealth and joyful with good fortunate. But the life of the Jadhagar runs totally different. Ever after having Dharma Karmathi Yogam, he working for low remuneration. Orbiting the Lagnathipathy at Sugasthanm he wandering for lack of money and economical problems to solve. At the 7th bava capricorn, the Karagathipathy Venus itself orbits, but the Jadhagar’s wife got divorced. Why these all inconvenience and what are the rules of planet makes him to ruin. The result follows:

While on birth the Saturn retrograded in 9th bava and conjunct with Ragu, the child grows to his father’s elder brother up to his Graduation. The life in the early stage and youth period with his Uncle was well and smooth. That is up to Ragu Dasa period. After finishing his graduation on Guru Dasa he got a job at private company and joined to his father. By the end of Sukra Bhuthi in Guru Dasa he got married August in the year 1998. And he lost his job and refused to go any job further. It irritates his wife and after three years of family life there no sign of having kid. His wife felt un satisfaction in the family life and went to court and got divorce from him in the year 2001. After that also his family life becomes as mirage. Why it happens?. The analyzed results given below..

- The 9th bava lord, Bhayathipathy orbits 12th bava to the Moon. Which claims Sagatai Yogam as we explained. So the life and job he got and left, again he got and left. The same way his life and financial position also goes ups and downs.
- The Kalathirakaragan Venus itself transits at 7th bava claims Karako bava nasthi, which claims his wife’s divorce. And the family life couldn’t be settled down.
- Again the 9th bava lord orbits at 3rd bava, conjunct with Kethu and Mars the 8th bava lord to the 3rd bava receives the direct aspects of Saturn which is conjunct with Ragu at 9th bava is significant indication of spoils the karagathuvam of Jupiter. That is specially finance and Children.
- Being the Ascent Cancer, the enmity lord Saturn orbits at 9th bava/Packyasthanm conjunct with Ragu by its direct aspect to the 3rd bava gives the Jadhagar a laziness in any field, results unfortunate.
- The Trine lords of this horoscope, Mars and Jupiter both are conjunct with Kethu in 3rd bava also a great draw back.
- And finally Laganathipathy receives no aspects or Conjunct with any benefic planet, the Venus lord of Libra/Tulam 4th bava, (where the Lagnathipathy Moon transits), orbits at Vedhagan Saturn’s house Capricorn, thus the Lagnam and the Moon lost its strength/debilitated.

Conclusion:

With the brief analyze, the importance of the Ascendant has been identified. There are some points is noted down, the situations or the transits which debilitation the Ascendant. First is the Ascendant falls in the mid-point of Ragu and Kethu, then the any type of yogam gets debilitated. Second, if there is a conjunct of Mars and Saturn the Bava has been affected much and becomes no use of its karakathuvam to the Ascendant. Third any bava falls in Papakarthari yogam then the bava is debilitated. Fourth, enmity planets orbits themselves within five degree, then the bava and the bavas of the planets are give unfortunate results. Fifth, if the transaction between malefic bava are not good to each other, then there is no use of transaction. In woman’s horoscope if the 9th bava not gets any benefic planet or its aspect, then the benefit of any benefic yogam doesn’t works. So, it is important to predict any horoscope, the thorough check of yogams, whether, it is benefic and do the position to benefit.

Notes:

La	: Lagnam/Ascent	Su	: Sun	Mo	: Moon
Ma	: Mars	Me	: Mercury	Ju	: Jupiter
Ve	: Venus	Sa	: Saturn	Ra	: Ragu
Ke	: Kethu	()	: Retrograded/Preverted.		

References:

1. Vedhalinga Pattar’s Jadhaga Parijathagam
2. Yavanachariyar’s Jothida Yavana Kaviyam
3. Manthereswarar’s Paladeepikai